

Test for mathematical abilities of LLMs

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We consider two graphs, a sample of flower snark [1], published by Rufus Isaacs in 1975, and graph constructed by Emanuels Grinbergs in 1972 [2,3,4,5].

Prove that both graphs are isomorphic. The proof should fit in a single line, preferably no longer than five words.

Take it as a test to compare different LLMs with respect to their ability to solve simple mathematical problems.

References

1. Flower snark, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flower_snark
2. Emanuels Grinbergs, Some threeconnected graphs and their families without Hamiltonian cycles, <https://vixra.org/pdf/2512.0096v1.pdf>
3. Emanuels Grinbergs Some threeconnected graphs and their families without Hamiltonian cycles, <http://dSPACE.lu.lv/server/api/core/bitstreams/bb15b1b9-1247-4f7b-b126-4680f6b907d7/content>
4. Emanuels Grinbergs, Notes in the graph theory. A manuscript (with flower snark J5) , <http://dSPACE.lu.lv/server/api/core/bitstreams/5fa08c08-8c03-4c9c-bbed-cafcae15b92/content>
5. The legacy of Emanuels Grinbergs: papers and scientic manuscript facsimiles. <https://www.ltn.lv/~dainize/MathPages/graphs.hypergraphs/Grinbergs/sci.mscrs.legacy.pdf>

